

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

20250207-ProCleanLakes- D1.6. Map of existing solutions for remediation and protection of European Natural Lakes (ENL)-V4

Funded by
the European Union

Project: 101157886 | HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-04 | www.procleanlakes.eu

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Reason(s) for data analysis: *The data was collected within project ProCleanLakes.*

Creation date of file(s): *07/02/2025*

Used method(s): *Literature review and research, 12 European Natural Lakes were researched as case studies.*

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools:

- *Zotero for references*
- *Microsoft Excel, Microsoft Office package*
- *Google Earth My Map*

Data:

- *20250207-ProCleanLakes-D1.6. Map of existing solutions for remediation and protection of European Natural Lakes (ENL)-V1.csv*
 - *Qualitative data collected from literature research*

Code:

- *20250207-ProCleanLakes-D1.6. Map of existing solutions for remediation and protection of European Natural Lakes (ENL)-V1.r*

Additional files:

- *Additional Maps are provided in the annex of the Document.*
- *No further additional files were produced.*

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Notes: This deliverable has not yet been approved by the European Commission